

Extraction and Purification of Chlorogenic Acid from Coffee Beans and Detection Its Role as Antifungal Agent

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ABSTRACT

In order to describe the coffee bean extract's chlorogenic acid, the current study will employ appropriate techniques such as glass column extraction with various solvents and isopropanol. It has been found that water is more effective than other solvents in extracting chlorogenic acid from coffee beans, which is then purified using a silica column. Chlorogenic acid has a retention period of 4.4 minutes in HPLC analysis, and its maximum absorbance is seen at $\lambda_{\max}$ 330 nm in UV-Vis spectra. Chlorogenic acid's functional groups were determined using FTIR, showing the presence of carboxyl and hydroxyl groups. Compared to other species of *Candida*, *C. albicans* has a larger percentage of genitourinary candidiasis cases. As an antifungal medication, chlorogenic acid was more effective against *Candida* spp. than fluconazole. In order that chlorogenic acid has been shown to be a viable lead compound for the synthesis of bioactive substitutes for the treatment of fungus infections.

1. Introduction

Coffee is a wonderful beverage with many health benefits, including its ability to function as an antioxidant (1). Chlorogenic acid is the primary ingredient in green coffee extract (2). It is a member of the hydroxycinnamic acid family of phenolic compounds. Many higher plants, including strawberries, blueberries, pineapples, sunflowers, and so on, contain chlorogenic acid (3,4). However, because of their high phenol content, green coffee beans—especially raw Arabica coffee—have a higher concentration of it (3). A significant class of phenolic chemicals, chlorogenic acids have antioxidant and antibacterial properties that make them useful as

a natural food preservative (4,5). In addition to its pharmacological qualities, which include anti-inflammatory, anti-obesity, neuroprotective, anti-diabetic, antioxidant, and anti-cancerous capabilities (4,6).

Candida species are always important from a medical standpoint. They can be opportunistic and pose a serious risk of systemic infections and persistent mucocutaneous infections in people with weakened immune systems (7, 8). Humans can develop genitourinary candidiasis, which includes oral candidiasis, candiduria in the digestive system in both sexes, in women, vaginal

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candidiasis; in men, balanoposthitis and balanitis (9). *Candida* species are present in humans. contains a number of virulence characteristics that promote pathogenicities, including the ability to adhere to different tissues and inanimate surfaces, the creation of biofilms, the ability to switch phenotypic, dimorphism, and the production of hydrolytic enzymes(10).The current study's goal was to synthesis, describe, and use chlorogenic acid as an antifungal agent.

2. Materials and Methods

Preparation of coffee beans powder

To get a consistent texture, ground coffee beans were filtered through a sieve.

Extraction of chlorogenic acid

Chlorogenic acid was extracted using a solvent in accordance with (11). To extract chlorogenic acid from the ground coffee powder, A glass column extraction was filled with roughly 10 g of the ground coffee bean after it was weighed. Then, 100 mL of isopropanol: water, ethanol: water, and butanol: water were added at a ratio of 1:10, along with 2 g of activated carbon. To completely rule out oxidation, the mixture was next magnetically agitated for 50 minutes at 80°C in the dark. After cooling, filter paper was used to filter the mixture. The filtrate underwent a 15-minute centrifugation at 3500 rpm. The extract was then emptied and subjected to a 50°C rotary evaporator distillation process and stored at 4°C was the extract.

Chlorogenic acid content

By using the chlorogenic acid standard curve, the resulting sample's chlorogenic acid content was calculated. To do this, 0.01 g of chlorogenic acid standard was dissolved in 100 ml of distilled water, and serial dilutions of working standards at 0.1, 2.5, 5, 10, 50, and 100 ppm were created (12). The absorbency was measured at 290 nm, and the chlorogenic acid concentration (mg/ml) was calculated using the following formula: $y = 7223x - 5982$.

Purification of Chlorogenic acid

A silica gel column was used for further chromatographic purification of the concentrated sample. Prior to gradient elution with 10, 20, 30,

40, 50%, and 60% ethanol, the column was first eluted with pure water. Chlorogenic acid content was determined for each fraction (13).**Characterization of Chlorogenic acid**

1- HPLC analysis

Gradient elution was used for HPLC analysis for the purified and standard chlorogenic acids with a flow rate of 1.2 mL/min. Acetonitrile, bidistilled water, and phosphoric acid made up the mobile phase composition.

2- UV-Visspectrometer

The pure chlorogenic acid was evaluated in the 175–400 nm wavelength range using the UV-Visspectrometer.

3- FTIR spectrum

Using an FTIR spectrometer, the functional groups in the purified and standard chlorogenic acids were identified by measuring their FTIR spectra. The scan range for these samples was 1000–4000 cm^{-1} wave number.

Collection and identification of *Candida* spp.

A total of forty-five distinct urine clinical specimens were sent for analysis in the lab. The specimens were originally diagnosed by culture on Sabouraud dextrose agar, Gram stain, and wet mount. On the Sabouraud dextrose agar, any discernible vegetation was processed in order to identify the species. Macroscopic inspection, followed by Gram stain, the ability to form the germ tube, and hydrolysis of urea were carried out on an isolated colony. Multiple species of *Candida* were identified based on the shape of growth and color of the isolates on CHROM agar media (14).

Antifungal activity of chlorogenic acid

Using the disc diffusion method, the antifungal activity of 25 μg of fuconazole and 25 μg of chlorogenic acid was evaluated against all *Candida* isolates. To prepare the inoculum, five colonies of growth were suspended in five milliliters of normal saline, and a measurement of the turbidity was made in relation to the 0.5 McFarland Standard.

The suspension of the inoculum was immersed in a cotton swab, which was subsequently uniformly distributed over Mueller-Hinton agar that was enhanced with 2% glucose and 5 µg/ml methylene blue.

(15). The infected media were covered with antifungal discs that contained 25 µg of fuconazole and 25 µg of chlorogenic acid and incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. The zone of inhibition surrounding the disc was assessed.

3. Results and discussion

Extraction of chlorogenic acid

Coffee beans were ground, then heated in various solvents for varying lengths of time, up to 50 minutes, during the extraction process. The findings indicated in figure (1) that, in comparison to the other solvent systems, the solvent system containing isopropanol and water produced the highest concentration of chlorogenic acid (2.6 mg/ml) after 40 minutes.

Figure(1):Extraction of chlorogenic acid with different extraction solvents systems and times

Coffee beans have less chlorogenic acid when roasted at higher temperatures by encouraging the dissolution of the acid's carbon-carbon bonds, which subsequently results in isomerization and deterioration (16). The origin and variety of coffee were additional factors that affected the quantity of chlorogenic acid (11).

Purification of chlorogenic acid

As reported in figure (2) the chlorogenic acid was eluted with 20% ethanol and yielded 3.7 mg/ml when the silica column was filled with the acid and eluted with distilled water before being gradient-eluted with ethanol concentrations.

Figure(2): Purification of chlorogenic acid with silica gel chromatography

Characterization of chlorogenic acid

1- HPLC analysis

Both the standard chlorogenic acid and the pure extract of coffee beans that contain chlorogenic acid were subjected to the current HPLC technique. Figure (3) shows that the pure chlorogenic acid had a retention duration of 4.2 minutes, but the standard of chlorogenic acid appeared after 4.4 minutes.

Figure(3): HPLC analysis of (a) the standard chlorogenic acid, (b) purified chlorogenic acid from coffee beans

2- UV-Vis spectrometer

When the chlorogenic acid content of coffee beans was directly measured using UV-Vis spectroscopy, the results revealed that the greatest peak appeared at 330 nm, as shown in figure (4). A peak was seen in the 300–350 nm range, and this peak matches the peak of the compound chlorogenic acid (17, 18).

Figure(4): UV-Vis spectrometer of purified chlorogenic acid from coffee beans

3-FTIR spectrum

Figure (5) displays the chlorogenic acid FTIR spectrum. The O-H vibration is responsible for the distinctive broad absorption peak of chlorogenic acid, which was detected at 3317 cm^{-1} . While the aromatic ring stretch vibrations at 1603 and 1500 are related to the carboxyl C-O vibration peak at 1681.

Figure(5): FTIR spectrum of (a) the standard chlorogenic acid, (b) purified chlorogenic acid from coffee beans

FTIR was used to analyze the chlorogenic acid extract from the leaves of *Morus alba*. According to (19, 20), It was suggested that the hydroxyl, carboxyl, and carbonyl groups of chlorogenic acid were its principal functional groups.

Collection and identification of *Candida* spp.

Several *Candida* species were recovered from urine infections; as shown in figure (6), these included 4 *Candida albicans* isolates (50%), 2 *Candida parapsilosis* isolates (25%), 1 *Candida glabrata* isolate (12.5%), and 1 *Candida krusei* isolate (12.5%).

Figure(6): Percentage of *Candida* spp. isolation from genitourinary candidiasis

Candida species include *Candida tropicalis*, *Candida albicans*, *Candida krusei*, and possibly *Candida glabrata*, can be found using the chromogenic medium CHROM agar *Candida*. The ability of CHROM agar *Candida* to identify candiduria in high-risk individuals and the possible application of this knowledge in guiding the first course of antifungal treatment in individuals subsequently found to have candidaemia (21). Since *Candida* ssp. is the most common opportunistic mycosis worldwide and a major contributor to nosocomial urinary tract infections, oral candidiasis, and genitourinary candidiasis, it is of medical significance. A number of variables, including age, sex, and host-pathogen immunity, influence the progression of *Candida* spp. infection (22).

Antifungal activity of chlorogenic acid

Fuconazole and chlorogenic acid's antifungal activities were assessed using the agar well diffusion method. As shown in figure (7), the

current analysis found that fuconazole, with diameters ranging from 11 to 21 mm, and chlorogenic acid, with diameters ranging from 16 to 32 mm, had better antifungal activity against isolates of *Candida albicans* and *C. glabrata*. *Candida* pathogenesis is impacted by the synthesis of hypha and biofilm, the release of specific enzymes, and adhesion to the tissues of the host (23).

When tested in vitro against *Candida* strains, chlorogenic acid demonstrated antifungal activity. This resulted in decreased cell viability, an increased risk of mitochondrial depolarization and the generation of reactive oxygen species, DNA fragmentation, and phosphatidylserine externalization, all of which pointed to an apoptotic process(24). It is also possible that chlorogenic acid exerts antifungal activity by altering the structure of the cell membrane (24). The investigation came to the conclusion that genitourinary candidiasis might be avoided by using chlorogenic acid.

Figure (7); Effect of of chlorogenic acid and fluconazole on *Candida* spp.

4. Conclusion

It has been discovered that water, an isopropanol, is more efficient at extracting chlorogenic acid from coffee bean extract. Chlorogenic acid exhibits promise as a bioactive substitute for the management of fungal infections, including genitourinary candidiasis resulting from *Candida* species.

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